

Relevant Stakeholders in Environmental Management Organization: The Case of Industries Três Rios/ RJ

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Abstract—The intense process of economic acceleration, expansion of industrial activities and capitalism, combined with population growth, while promoting the development, bring environmental consequences and dynamics of locations. It can be seen that society is seeking to break with old paradigms of capitalist society, seeking to reconcile growth with sustainable development, with a change of mentality of the stakeholders of the production process (shareholders, employees, suppliers, customers, governments, and neighbors, groups citizens and the public in general). In this context, this research aims to map the stakeholders interested in environmental management in industries located in the city of *Três Rios/RJ*. The city of *Três Rios* is located in South-Central region of the state of Rio de Janeiro - Brazil. Methodological resources used refer to descriptive and field research, whose nature is qualitative and quantitative. It is also of multicases studies in the study area, and the data collection occurred by means of semi-structured questionnaires and interviews with employees related to the environmental area of the industries located in *Três Rios* and registered at the Federation of Industries the State of Rio de Janeiro - FIRJAN in the version of 2013 and active in federal revenue. Through this research it observed, among other things, the stakeholders involved in the environmental management process of “Três Rios” industry respondents, and those responding to the demands of environmental management.

Keywords—Environmental management, environmental practices, industry, stakeholders.

I. INTRODUCTION

THE expansion of industrial activities and capitalism, associated with population growth occurred in the XX fostered the process of acceleration of the Brazilian economy [1]. This process has brought environmental consequences and dynamics of locations, and, in the 90s, the focus and the concern of industries as the product is modified and extended to the activities involved in the production, such as social issues, waste management industrial and natural resource. Companies now start to take responsibility for the natural environment and using that impact, seeking then adapts to

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sustainable production patterns towards a harmonious integration of society with ecology.

The relationship between the company and society is elevated to a higher level, because with this new vision, “*the company must assess and treat impacts, existing and potential, of their products, processes and facilities*” [2]. As a result of this development process has grown proportionately production volumes, the generation of industrial quantities of waste higher or lower risk for the environment and consumption of greater amount of natural resources. In this context, arrived on the scene the main agents involved in the operation of companies, stakeholders, which have direct influence on companies, and also to environmental causes in production processes. Managers from different areas have turned their attention to environmental and sustainability issues, this theme running through the sense of ecological and social responsibility having significant impacts on the image conveyed by the organization and consequently in production and profits from it. This concern for the natural environment makes the issue be incorporated into actions and business and government speeches, seeing solutions to the problem.

The question of this research is: *What are the major stakeholders in decision-making of corporate environmental management and how “Três Rios” industries are responding to the demands of the same?* This work aims to determine who the relevant stakeholders are in the environmental management process at the industries in “Três Rios” - Rio de Janeiro - Brazil. Therefore, we sought to analyze who are the main stakeholders of the surveyed industries, as well as how the company responds to them with regard to environmental management through the application of questionnaires previously tested and applied from March to June 2014.

This article is divided into five parts, the first being the introduction that presents the initial considerations and the purpose to which the work is proposed. The second deals with the methodological procedures used in this study and an overview of the study area. The third presents the literature review on environmental issues, followed by case study, which includes search results. Finally, are presented the conclusions and the references.

II. METHODOLOGICAL PROCEDURES

The research methodology used in this study, is dedicated to data collection procedures, analysis of the data and methodological framework of the research, aiming to achieve the proposed objective. This study came from the research problem for the formulation of a literature review framework

regarding environmental issues. This survey gathered and compiled several sources of secondary reference, articles, books; texts researched on the internet and in newspapers, published materials on the topic discussed. Moreover, it is a descriptive study, which exposes characteristics and achievements of a population (industries stakeholders in relation to environmental management) [3], [4]. It is classified as a multicases study, since it aims to map the stakeholders interested in environmental management in industries located in “Três Rios”/RJ/BR. “Três Rios” - RJ is located in South-Central region of the state of Rio de Janeiro - Brazil, bordering the state of “Minas Gerais” (Fig. 1). “Três Rios” has about 78,000 inhabitants, in addition to population floating, and has this name due to the meeting of three rivers (Piabanha, Paraibuna and Paraíba do Sul) in its territory, forming the only triple delta in Latin America [5].

Fig. 1 Três Rios – RJ– Brazil

The present work is structured starting from the research problem to a literature review, which underlies and directs the steps of the research. After the construction of the literature review, the object of research industries were selected, based on the record of the Federation of Industries of Rio de Janeiro - FIRJAN in the version 2013. Sifting and screening was performed of industries located in “Três Rios” and registered in FIRJAN, which were divided into Micro company (up to 19 employees); Small company (20-99 employees); Medium company (100-499 employees); Large company (500 employees upwards), taking into account the parameter of the Support Service for Micro and Small Enterprises - SEBRAE. “Três Rios” had in 2013 in the register of FIRJAN, with 236 industries, 151 micro companies, 55 small, 25 medium, 5 large and 3 without the number of employees disclosed.

From the verification of the data contained in the register of FIRJAN, confirmation of activity and the total number of active companies with assistance from the IRS website was held, which maintains a constant update on the status of industries, and this was reduced to 138 active in period researched. Thus, it can be said that “Três Rios” had, during the study period, with 77 micro companies, 38 small, 22 medium, 1 large. The companies selected to be part of the survey, and are of different sizes, are of different activity sectors (food, textiles and clothing, chemical, rubber and plastic, nonmetallic minerals, metallurgy, machinery and equipment, motor vehicles, trailers and bodies, various products, infrastructure, construction and repair).

After defining the population and survey sample, was

drawn up the data collection tool (questionnaire), the qualitative and quantitative, to be applied to employees of the operational area of the industries and the integral members of the research area. The questionnaire was pre-tested with 27 undergraduate course in Environmental Management, the Federal Rural University of Rio de Janeiro - UFRRJ - RJ / BR, allowing the correction of distortions for further application.

Made the necessary adjustments, the questionnaire was also pretested with 12 employees in the industrial sector of a company in the petrochemical branch, located in the city of Macaé - RJ / BR, totaling 25% of employees surveyed sector. From this the digital questionnaire was made available in the Google Docs platform to be sent to contacts, after creating an email in Gmail intended solely to research, and to be the channel and means of communication with industry.

Data collection took place from March to June 2014, and the results were analyzed qualitative and quantitatively. Given the difficulties of obtaining return on the part of respondents to the questionnaire were also made telephone contacts with a view to increase participation in research. Thus, it obtained 5.14% return on questionnaires sent. Thus, the profiles of the responding industries are shown in Table I.

As regards the assessment and analysis of data, descriptive instruments were used, coupled with software that enabled the preparation of charts and analysis of results.

TABLE I
 PROFILE OF RESPONDENT COMPANIES

Business Sector	Companies	%
Manufacture of other transport equipment, except motor vehicles	Small	14,29
Manufacture of non-metallic mineral products	Small	14,29
Manufacture of metal products, except machinery and equipment	Medium	14,29
Manufacture of food products	Medium	14,29
Manufacture of machinery, appliances and equipment	Micro	14,29
No identified	-	28,57

III. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Environmental Conferences

The configuration of the first public conference on environmental issues was given by the new sensitivity initiated by the deterioration of the welfare, health and life, with the belief that being on the margins of pollution and environmental degradation would also be exposed to diseases, with losses in their quality of life. The first laws, conferences and environmental initiatives that have emerged in the world alerting the importance of the environment to its healthy maintenance are set out.

The first forest law was enacted in the city of Ur, in Sumer, in the year 2700 BC, pioneering the subject covering environmental preservation. A few centuries later, in AD 80, the Roman senate passed a law to protect water, store during the dry season and allow its use for the cleaning of streets and sewers [6].

In Europe, the first ecological process that is known,

occurred in Finale - Italy, in 1700, this was against a mercuric chloride factory that gave off toxic gases, damaging the quality of life of local people. Years later, one of the countries currently most rich and developed world, the United States of America (USA) was the first to create a national park for the purpose of environmental preservation and a recreation area for the population. It was in 1872 that the Yellowstone National Park - USA was created, an important step for environmental stamp issues as soon as this concept has spread to several countries and other parks have also emerged, contributing to the preservation of resources various natural ecosystems [6].

Since the 1960s conferences are held about the impasse experienced by companies and governments in an attempt to reconcile economic growth and environmental sustainability [7]-[15].

After the early XX century and the first environmental initiatives, creations of "N.G.Os" and national parks, the importance of the environment for humanity was intensified, generating specific laws to address this issue. In 1962, the launch of the book "Silent Spring", the writer and North American biologist Rachel Carson, warned about the harmful effects of numerous human actions on the environment, such as the use of pesticides and insecticides. Before the release of the book, there were a large number of people concerned about the degradation of nature by human actions, but the political nature of the environmental movement gained strength after the impact of the book. As a result of this impact, some years later, countries such as Hungary, Norway, Sweden, Germany and the United States, have banned the use of insecticides such as dichloro-difeniltricloroetano ("D.D.T.").

Ten years after the launch of the book "Silent Spring" in 1972, was the first United Nations Conference on Environment and Development in Stockholm, Sweden. Environmental issues raised were related to air pollution, water and soil, which were consequences of the industrialization process. This meeting was intended to encourage the government and international organizations action to promote environmental protection of human actions [1].

In the same year of the Stockholm Conference, the Club of Rome, a group formed in 1968 by intellectuals, scientists and politicians who watched and discussed on sustainable development, published "The Limits to Growth," a book that related and problematized population growth the world with the depletion of natural resources. Years later, in 1983, the United Nations created the World Commission on Environment and Development, better known as the Brundtland Commission, which in 1987 published the Brundtland Report or Our Common Future, who scored the definition of sustainable development [16]. The Brundtland Report introduced the concept of equality between rich and poor, developed and developing countries, current and future generations, and showed a close and intertwined relationship between economy and ecology.

International environmental conferences became common

and an increasing relevance. In 1992, the Brazilian city of Rio de Janeiro hosted the Eco-92 or "Earth Summit". The conference adopted Agenda 21, which is a program for the purpose of "away" the world of an unsustainable economic development.

Ten years after the Eco-92 and sixteen years of the nuclear accident in Chernobyl, the "World Summit on Sustainable Development" was held in the city of Johannesburg in South Africa, aiming to take stock of the achievements, challenges and new issues environmental problems that have emerged since the last summit. The discussion was also focused on actions related to poverty eradication, globalization and energy issues, such as Clean Development Mechanisms ("C.D.M.") and the Kyoto Protocol (which was signed in 1997, proposing the reduction of carbon dioxide emissions and encouraging reforestation) and climate change, among others [1].

Marking the twentieth birthday of the First United Nations Conference on Environment and Development in Stockholm, was the United Nations Conference on Sustainable Development (Rio + 20) in 2012 in Rio de Janeiro - Brazil, in which they assessed progress since the last conference in 2002 in South Africa, and to evaluate the existing shortcomings in government management of each country on natural resources and develop future perspectives on environmental issues. These conferences have had as a main objective to draw attention not only of governments, but also civil society, for the environment, and practice more and more sustainability in the preservation and conservation of natural resources.

B. Environmentalism in Brazil

Brazil had its territory discovered in the late XV century and early XVI century, the result of political and economic pressure that was being developed on Portugal and Spain by other European nations. While the settler colonies of America's northern hemisphere attracted the colonists with advertisements and deceptions [17] for the fostering of business and politics, Brazil, in the same period, continued to be a source of wealth for Portugal, and then settled for exploitation of natural resources.

Noting the disordered extraction of natural resources, the first Brazilian forestry legislation was made on native plant species in the country, Brazil wood. In order to set up special permissions for the cutting of Brazil wood was prepared in December 1605, the "Charter of Appeal and House of Brazil", causing the deforestation was a constant [6].

After years of exploitation of minerals and rare or economically significant species for Portugal, Brazil was then used to subsidize planting of exotic species such as sugarcane and coffee, which were important for the international market [18]. Large sugar and coffee farms labor would need to make the crops and harvest them, this need was supplied by the slave trade arising Africa. This trade has generated great wealth for planters; causing crops take greater proportions and also more exhausting the soil. Slavery would have many negative aspects for guidance as well as export dependence on world markets [19].

The reality of Brazilian agriculture, after years of land use, also became different and with the tired soil and hand endearing work, maintaining the old production was unfeasible [18]. As this fact took hold in the year 1797, the first charter on conservation of forests and woods was signed, stating the precaution with the preservation of Brazilian forests [6]. However, the environmental issue in Brazil only began to gain greater importance later centuries, in fact, with the Stockholm Conference in 1972, as we have said, was the scene of one of the first and most important meetings to talk about the environment in consideration of the developmental movement. Throughout the 70s and especially in the early 80s, some social problems have worsened, severe distortions as the concentration of income and property, making it clear that the developmental promises did not materialize. Thus, this development crisis turned out to boost public awareness of environmental degradation. The devastation in the Amazon, "Cerrado" and almost complete elimination of the Atlantic Forest in Brazilian soil, boosted big fights against actions that interfere in the environment, with support from international "N.G.Os." to Brazilian also showing the global concern about the environment in Brazil [20].

One of the major landmarks to Brazil and to environmentalism was with the formation of the Constituent Assembly of 1988 even with a single fully environmentalist candidate, the receptivity of the environmental issue was big, then turning to new environmental legislation one of the most advanced in the world [20].

C. Environment and Sustainability

There are different visions and conceptions of the environment, which are constantly being modified. This subject was the basis of different discussions, being covered from its economic bias to the social bias. Since the beginning of its operation arising on the European continent, the environment was seen as something to be dominated by man, considered threatening and unsightly. The development of human progress was measured by their ability to dominate this natural world as it was associated with making a profit, as it was seen only as a source of resources and practices of civilizing processes. A civilized environment was represented by progress at anthropocentrism, the manners and the sophistication. The natural environment, as a result, was synonymous with barbarity and ignorance.

The Industrial Revolution took place in England, was the reason for such environmental degradation of the time. As a result of this revolution was the growing number of factories, increased use of coal, increasing population in urban areas, peasant expropriation, lack of sanitation, wide spread of epidemics, unhealthy living conditions, among other problems, causing the destruction of landscapes, species, ecosystems and even the change in the population's quality of life, affecting mainly public health.

It was from the XVIII century which began a major change concerning the thought of humanity on the environment, starting thus a new sensibility, which was focused on the enhancement of plant, animal and natural landscapes. This

new sensitivity was also initiated by the deterioration of the welfare, health and bourgeois life of the time, that even with this social level, believing they are on the margins of pollution and environmental degradation would also be exposed to these problems, with losses in their quality life.

In Brazil, only in the 90s, mainly from the Rio 92 environmental issues entered in the agenda of all social groups. It is noticed that the company is seeking to solve a problem, "*combine growth with quality of life, to grow without destroying, to ensure its futurity*"[21], seeking to reconcile growth with economic development, causing a break from the classic conflict between economy and ecology.

Companies are now developing strategic processes and marketing strategies not only through its technical-economic dimension, but mainly as an institutional political game of legitimizing their competitive strategies.

"Companies are realizing that to win and retain customers in an increasingly conscious of environmental issues market, the products themselves have to be cleaner". [22]

Reference [23] states that some companies realize that "*cause damage to the environment could undermine their competitiveness*". Reference [24] identifies five factors as the main reasons responsible for the environmental awareness of companies:

- Companies realize they can gain in production or saving financial resources to environmental improvement;
- The existence of environmental laws inhibit devastating actions;
- Civil society has increased the relative pressure on environmental issues;
- The market demands products that are made from environmentally sustainable manner;
- Financial investors have begun to value company shares environmentally correct.

One of the main variables that begins to emerge as a source of gaining competitive advantage is related to environmental aspects: how the company relates to the environment, the management of effluents, waste and by-products of manufacturing goods, obtaining raw materials and the installation of a production unit in a particular location, are increasingly relevant topics in corporate image building to society. It is thus an extension identifying the stakeholders that influence and even change the view of interaction between the company and society. This process requires an increase in the discussion of the formulation of corporate strategy, for business management will now be centered set of interests of the parties involved, seeking excellence through quality in relations and the economic, social and environmental sustainability.

Organizations and society are realizing that climate change, environmental change and rampant exploitation of the environment present systemic risks to the business and the maintenance of life on Earth. Thus, there is increasing motion preservation of the environment.

D. Stakeholders

Stakeholders are individuals, groups or organizations that can affect, positively or negatively, or whose interests may be affected by the company [25]-[28]. Organizations have different types of stakeholders, enabling variations thereof during its life cycle and whose neglect of these can take the organization to the decline [29].

Any activity, strategy or even projects implemented by the organizations have a set of entities or persons with interests in being developed or its results. These public can be influenced by organizations or even influence them. Depending on the interests, stakeholders can take a strategic position and engaged in the proposed organization or, in extreme cases, to take his break, contributing to its failure. The success or failure of a project to be implemented in the organization is related to the perception of stakeholders on the value created by the project and the nature of the relationship with the team involved in it [30].

If in the past the focus was directed to dimensions as development and control of scope, schedule and budget, currently we see is the need to balance control and strengthening relationships with stakeholders.

It is an extension of identifying stakeholders that will change the vision of interaction between the organization and society. This process will require an increase in the discussion of the formulation of corporate strategy, for business management will now be centered set of interests of the parties involved, seeking excellence through quality in relations and the economic, social and environmental sustainability.

One can divide the categories of stakeholders from the business units of: (i) internal; (ii) external; (iii) financial; (iv) consumers; (v) and supplies (Fig. 2).

Arises a new relationship network, with new forms of interaction with the organization's interest groups [10]. Thus, it is observed that the area where the companies operate has become more complex with the development of new organizational relationships with agents previously spurned.

Fig. 2 Types of Stakeholders

IV. RESULTS

Through this research we found that the majority (83%) of respondents to date performs an environmental project, namely mainly to improve water treatment and sewage, waste sorting, multipliers in environmental education, among others. Only 17% did not perform any environmental project.

Thus, with regard to activities involving environmental issues in business, it was found that the "Três Rios" industries which answered the survey carry out activities such as recycling, water treatment and sewage, project environmental education and selective collection (Fig. 3) pointing out the importance of environmental issues for the company. However, difficulties were identified found for the realization of these environmental activities, such as lack of technical information, missing follow environmental regulations and the cost of labor, skilled labor, especially for small businesses.

Fig. 3 Expertise in Environmental and Social area

Regarding the main reasons that has led respondents industries to implement environmental practices, the three most marked alternatives were: (i) the search for licensing; (ii) the front company's image enhancement to consumers and / or company; and (iii) the change of environmental policy the same. When asked about quest to obtain environmental certification or already have, 57% of respondents wish to obtain certification in the future and 43% are interviewing for right now (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4 Certification achievement

The response shows that industries which responded to the survey have the following main stakeholders involved in the process of environmental actions, the government - that through the role of legislator and controller makes the industries have some kind of environmental performance; and

consumers - pressing the industries for better products, quality and commitment to environmental initiatives, targeting the sources of consumption. These data point out that the State through legislative and supervisory role and consumers are the main stakeholders in the environmental management process. Thus it can be seen that regardless of the size of the company and its market, whether domestic or international, companies are concerned about environmental issues. However, often the concern with the environment is not explicit in all the survey respondents industries.

V. CONCLUSION

Environmental weathering, as eminent nowadays, tend to worsen further over the next decades. If there is no concern for the environment and the best man's relationship with nature, there may be an even greater scarcity of natural resources and a concussion in the economic, industrial and environmental model.

This study aimed to map the stakeholders of the environmental management process in industries located in "Três Rios" and see how managers respond to their demands. Thus, it found, among other things, that the research respondents industries have some environmental projects.

It is noticed that the industries that answered the questionnaire have as main stakeholders involved in the process of environmental actions, the government and consumers, the first of which acts as regulator of the activities of businesses and the second push for better products, quality and commitment to environmental initiatives, targeting the sources of consumption. It is noteworthy, therefore, the importance of developing environmental projects in order to achieve economic, social and sustainable development, especially in economic sectors that depend on the environment as a source of raw materials and energy.

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